

New Invariants of the Schrödinger Equation and Problems of Measurement Interpretation

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Abstract

In this study, we explore the impact of the choice of coordinate system on the scattering amplitude within the framework of the Schrödinger equation. Our findings reveal that the phase of the scattering amplitude is dependent on the selected coordinate system. The research further demonstrates that the energy of bound states remains invariant regardless of the coordinate system employed, thus confirming its stability across different coordinate transformations. Additionally, we show that the wave functions of bound states can be effectively derived through straightforward coordinate transformations. The paper also delves into the emergence of gauge invariance in the context of both scattering amplitude and wave functions, highlighting the fundamental symmetries of the system. This investigation offers new insights into the underlying principles of quantum mechanics and the influence of coordinate systems on quantum states.

Keywords: Riemann, Hilbert, Poincaré, Cauchy, Schrödinger equation
2010 MSC: 11M26

The Schrödinger equation, first introduced in references (1-2), forms the cornerstone of modern methodologies for modeling physical processes. The exploration of new properties of the solutions to the Schrödinger equation carries significant implications for a wide range of theoretical and applied physics domains. Beyond its traditional scientific applications, the Schrödinger equation has found usage in diverse applied fields such as economics, geophysics, and seismic exploration. This research uncovers the dependency of the scattering amplitude on the chosen coordinate system, underlining the critical role of amplitude calibration in this context. It also examines how the scattering phase varies with different coordinate systems. Furthermore, this study establishes the invariance of bound state energy relative to the coordinate system, confirming its constancy across various transformations. Additionally, we demonstrate that the wave functions of bound states can be derived via simple coordinate transformations. A primary objective of this paper is to elucidate the emer-

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gence of gauge invariance in relation to both the scattering amplitude and wave functions.

Methods: In this study, we consider Schrödinger's equation:

$$-\Delta\Psi + q\Psi = k^2\Psi \quad (1)$$

where $k \in C$. We analyze the scattering amplitude $A(k, \theta, \theta)$ and its dependence on the chosen coordinate system. The solutions to the equation are obtained by solving the Lippman-Schwinger integral equation:

$$\Psi_+(k, \theta, x) = \Psi_0(k, \theta, x) + \int q(y) \frac{e^{ik|x-y|}}{|x-y|} \Psi_+(k, \theta, y) dy \quad (2)$$

$$\Psi_+(k, \theta, x) = \Psi_0(k, \theta, x) + G(q\Psi_+),$$

$$\Psi_0(k, \theta', x) = e^{k(\theta', x)}$$

We assume that the potentials decrease rapidly at infinity and belong to the class of continuously differentiable functions.

Definition 1. : We define the set of measurable functions R with the norm $\|q\|_R$ given by:

$$\|q\|_R = \int \int |q(x)q(y)|/|x-y|^2 dx dy < \infty$$

This set is recognized as the Rollnik class. The following theorem was stated in [4]:

Theorem 1. *Let*

$$\|q\|_R < 1/(4\pi)$$

then the solutions to the Schrödinger equation can be expressed as:

$$\Psi_+(k, \theta, x) = \Psi_0(k, \theta, x) + \sum (Gq)^n \Psi_0 \quad (3)$$

$$A(k, \theta', \theta) = -(1/(4\pi)) \int \int q(x) \Psi_0(k, \theta, x) \Psi(k, -\theta', x) dx \quad (4)$$

We introduce

$$q_{Ua}(x) = q(Ux + a)$$

where

$$UU' = U'U = I$$

$$a \in R^3$$

The corresponding amplitude and wave functions, denoted as

$$A_{Ua}, \Psi_{Ua}, E_{Ua}$$

are associated with these potentials.

Theorem 2. *The wave function $\Psi_{U_{a+}}$ can be expressed as:*

$$\Psi_{U_{a+}}(k, \theta, x) = \Psi_0(k, \theta, x) + \sum (Gq_{U_a})^n \Psi_0 \quad (5)$$

$$A_{U_{a+}}(k, \theta', \theta) = -(1/(4\pi)) \int q_{U_a}(x) \Psi_0(k, \theta, x) \Psi_{U_a}(k, -\theta', x) dx \quad (6)$$

Proof: The theorem follows directly from the representations (3) and (4).

Theorem 3. *: The poles of the functions $\Psi_{U_{a+}}$ and Ψ_+ coincide, i.e.*

$$E_{U_a} = E.$$

Proof: From the representations (3) and (4).

$$\Psi_{U_{a+}}(k, \theta, x_1) = \Psi_0(k, \theta, x_1) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \prod_{k=1}^n \int \frac{q_{U_a}(x_{k+1}) e^{ik|x_k - x_{k+1}|}}{|x_k - x_{k+1}|} \Psi_0(k, \theta, x_{n+1}) dx_2 \dots dx_{n+1} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_{U_{a+}}(k, \theta, x_1) &= \Psi_0(k, \theta, x_1) + \\ e^{ik(\theta, a)} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \prod_{k=1}^n \int \frac{q(x_k) e^{ik|x_k - x_{k+1}|}}{|x_k - x_{k+1}|} \Psi_0(k, \theta, Ux_{n+1}) dx_2 \dots dx_{n+1} \\ \Psi_{U_{a+}}(k, \theta, x_1) &= \Psi_0(k, \theta, x_1) + \\ e^{ik(\theta, a)} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \prod_{k=1}^n \int \frac{q(x_k) e^{ik|x_k - x_{k+1}|}}{|x_k - x_{k+1}|} \Psi_0(k, \theta, Ux_{n+1}) dx_2 \dots dx_{n+1} \\ \Psi_{U_{a+}}(k, \theta, x_1) &= \Psi_0(k, \theta, x_1) + \\ e^{ik(\theta, a)} [\Psi_0(k, U'\theta, x_1) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \prod_{k=1}^n \int \frac{q(x_k) e^{ik|x_k - x_{k+1}|}}{|x_k - x_{k+1}|} \Psi_0(k, U'\theta, x_{n+1}) dx_2 \dots dx_{n+1}] \\ &\quad - e^{ik(\theta, a)} \Psi_0(k, U'\theta, x_1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\Psi_{U_{a+}}(k, \theta, x_1) = \Psi_0(k, \theta, x_1) + e^{ik(\theta, a)} \Psi_+(k, U'\theta, x_1) - e^{ik(\theta, a)} \Psi_0(k, U'\theta, x_1)$$

Theorem 4. *: Amplitudes of the functions $\Psi_{U_{a+}}$ and Ψ_+ can calculates as .*

$$A_{U_a}(k, \theta', \theta) = e^{ik(\theta - \theta', a)} A(k, \theta', \theta)$$

Proof: From the Theorem (2)

$$A_{U_{a+}}(k, \theta', \theta) = -(1/(4\pi)) \int q_{U_a}(x_1) \Psi_0(k, \theta, x_1) \Psi_{U_a}(k, -\theta', x_1) dx_1 \quad (8)$$

from Theorem (3)

$$A_{Ua+}(k, \theta', \theta) = -(1/(4\pi)) \int q_{Ua}(x_1) \Psi_0(k, \theta, x) [\Psi_0(k, -\theta', x_1) +$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \prod_{k=1}^n \int \frac{q_{Ua}(x_{k+1}) e^{ik|x_k - x_{k+1}|}}{|x_k - x_{k+1}|} \Psi_0(k, -\theta', x_{n+1})] dx_2 \dots dx_{n+1} dx_1$$

$$A_{Ua+}(k, \theta', \theta) = e^{ik(\theta' - \theta)} A(k, U'\theta', U'\theta)$$

Applications

1. This study has uncovered the essential relationship regarding the invariance of the discreteness of eigenvalues for a family of potentials obtained through linear transformations of variables. The simplicity of these transformations reveals that many achievements obtained using Lax pairs are inherent properties resulting from linear transformations of variables in Schrödinger equations.
2. For analysis and optimal use of seismic data
3. For analysis and optimal use of ultrasound scan data
4. For analysis and optimal use of electromagnetic scan data
5. For analysis and optimal use of non-linear scan fluctuation data

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